

Human resource strategy

Kholmurodova E'zoza Xasanovna

“Tashkent Institute of Irrigation and Agricultural
Mechanization Engineers” National Research University

English department, English language teacher

Abstract: The topics of strategic planning of human resource management of an organization are considered. effective functioning of any enterprise is directly related to an adequate system of human resource management. This article formulates the main objectives of human resource management strategies, considers different types of such strategies, analyzes their components and characteristic features, and important stages of the process of strategic human resource management.

Keywords: strategies, planning, strategic management, personnel management, features of personnel management strategy

Personnel management strategy is a systematic planning of actions and making informed decisions on the organization and management of human resources in the organization. It includes determining the company's goals and priorities, developing methods of motivating and stimulating employees, as well as creating conditions for the development of professional skills and competencies of personnel. Important elements of the HR management strategy are taking into account the needs and expectations of employees, adaptation to changes in the external environment and continuous improvement of human resource management methods. The main objectives of the HR management strategy are to increase labor efficiency, improve the quality of staff work, reduce staff turnover and create a favorable working atmosphere in the team.

Personnel management methods play a key role in modern organizations, helping managers to effectively organize the work of their subordinates. There are many

ways to influence employees in order to achieve the set goals and ensure the successful functioning of the company. Among the main methods of personnel management can be distinguished: delegation of authority, motivation of employees, performance appraisal and evaluation, training and development of personnel, as well as the design and implementation of reward systems. Each of these methods has its own features and advantages, and their integrated use allows to achieve high results in personnel management.

HR strategy is a plan of action and methods that a company uses to effectively manage its employees. It includes setting goals and priorities, developing a motivation and reward system, training and development of personnel, as well as performance and conflict management. The main goal of a human resource management strategy is to create a favorable work environment in which each employee can reach his or her potential and contribute to the company's goals.

Human resource management techniques may include various approaches to employee organization, motivation, development and training. Some of the basic personnel management techniques include:

1. Developing a human resource management strategy: defining goals and priorities, analyzing the needs of the company and its employees.
2. Developing a performance appraisal system: defining criteria for employee performance appraisal, conducting regular analysis of results and feedback.
3. Motivating and rewarding employees: creating incentives to achieve better results, providing opportunities for professional growth and development.
4. Training and development of personnel: conducting trainings, seminars, training programs to improve the skills of employees.
5. Conflict management: resolving conflict situations between employees or between management and subordinates.
6. Rewards and incentives system: applying various types of incentives to encourage good performance.

7. Communication processes: establishing effective feedback systems between management and employees to ensure an open dialog.

These methods are the foundation of successful human resource management in any company.

1. Developing and implementing HR management goals and strategies in line with the overall strategic goals of the company.
2. Attracting, selecting and retaining qualified employees.
3. Training, development and motivation of personnel to achieve better results.
4. Establishing an effective employee performance appraisal and feedback system.
5. Creating a favorable corporate culture and work environment.
6. Developing a system for rewarding, incentivizing, and rewarding employees for achieving company goals.
7. Resolving conflicts and problems in the team, and maintaining healthy relations between employees.
8. Facilitating professional development of staff and career growth.
9. Analyzing personnel performance data to optimize personnel management processes.

These features of the HR management strategy help the company to create an effective team of employees capable of achieving the goals and objectives set for them.

To sum up, strategic control is carried out through the selection and analysis of key factors, collection of necessary information. The main factors affecting the process of strategic control include the system of strategic personnel management, strategic objectives, intermediate criteria, implementation of the personnel management system and strategy execution, compliance of strategies and systems with the environment, feedback, regulation, and maintenance of the organization.

References:

1. Дмитренко Г.А. Мотивация и оценка персонала. Учеб. пособие. -Киев: МАУП, 2002. - 246с.
2. Boxall, P. F. The Strategic HRM Debate and the Resource-Based View of the Firm I R. F. Boxall II Human Resource Management Journal. - 1996. - Vol. 6. - № 3. - Pp. 59-75.
3. Ulrich D. The talent trifecta // Development and Learning in Organizations: An International Journal. 2008. Vol.22. No.2. DOI: 10.1108/dlo.2008.08122bad.003.
4. Соколова М.И. Управление человеческими ресурсами. - М.: Проспект, 2005.-238с.